

PARAMETRIC STUDY OF PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE GROWTH AT THE FIBER/MATRIX SCALE USING COHESIVE ZONE ELEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

A random microscale model of a fiber/matrix composite was used to predict the fracture properties to be used at the mesoscale. Cohesive zone elements were placed between every continuum element in the refined meshes. The effects of boundary conditions, RVE size, and microscale fracture properties on the predicted mesoscale properties were considered. Though more complex to implement, periodic boundary conditions were shown to predict more realistic crack paths than a much simpler set of boundary conditions. The RVE size had a significant effect on the predicted strain energy release rate but not the strength. As the RVE size increased, the predicted strain energy release rate increased, seemingly due to the more diffuse damage that can occur in larger RVE's. Since convergence of the critical strain energy release rate was not observed, it is unclear which RVE size is appropriate for microscale fracture analyses. The fiber/matrix interfacial strength has a significant effect on the predicted strength and G_{IC} . When the interface is weaker, most damage occurs along the fiber/matrix interfaces, and an increase of the interfacial strength results in a significant overall improvement of the predicted strength but little effect on the predicted G_{IC} . When the interface is stronger than the matrix, damage occurs both in the matrix and along the fiber/matrix interfaces, and an increase in the interfacial strength results in a moderate increase in predicted strength and G_{IC} .

1 INTRODUCTION

Using numerical models to understand the effects of fiber/matrix microstructural characteristics on the failure properties to be used at the mesoscale scale provides important insights needed to optimize materials for specific applications. This also reduces the need for expensive experimental study. Many models have been proposed to model the progression of damage in composite materials, but they tend to fall into two groups: those that model damage discretely and those that model damage in a diffuse manner. Cohesive zone models and continuum damage models are examples of these two approaches, respectively. The focus of this paper is cohesive zone based modeling. Cohesive zone models provide the benefit of not requiring an initial crack, which is required by virtual crack closure methods. However, they have typically been used at the mesoscale, so there is very limited experience in assessing the performance or proper usage at the fiber/matrix scale.

There are many parameters that can potentially affect the fracture properties predicted for use at the next larger scale, including matrix fracture properties, fiber/matrix interface fracture properties, volume fraction, and voids. Furthermore, there are characteristics of the model that can be important, including mesh refinement, the arrangement of fibers in the microstructure, RVE size, and the selected boundary conditions. A critical complication is that some of the properties needed in the micromechanics analyses are impossible to experimentally measure directly. Hence, an inverse analysis is needed. Understanding the sensitivity of the predicted properties to microscale constituent and geometric properties that are not known precisely helps quantify the uncertainty in the predictions. This paper will focus on the effects of

boundary conditions, number of realizations, RVE size, and fracture properties of the fiber/matrix interface on the predicted mesoscale fracture properties.

2 THEORY

The cohesive zone formulation used in this work is given along with the equations used to calculate the traction-separation law to be used that the next larger scale.

2.1 Cohesive Zone Formulation

Many cohesive formulations have been proposed using a variety of traction-separation laws that govern the opening [1-3]. A cohesive zone formulation can be used within mesh independent methods [4-6] or within standard FEA with interfacial elements placed between two continuum elements, which this paper considers. This paper employs Turon's bilinear mixed-mode cohesive zone model for the interfacial elements [1]. Turon proposed a bilinear traction-separation law with a very stiff linear behavior before the critical traction, t_c , or critical displacement, Δ_0 , is exceeded, at which point damage begins, as illustrated in Fig. Figure 1. In the damage regime of the traction-separation curve, the traction across the interface decreases linearly with the separation until the traction is reduced to zero, which occurs at Δ_f , and a further increase in separation continues to result in zero traction. Unloading from a point where damage has occurred (A in Fig. Figure 1) follows the line AO directly to the origin and no change in the damage state. An increase in separation will cause an increase in damage.

Figure 1: Bilinear traction-separation curve

The separation in the normal and tangential directions will be denoted by Δ_n and Δ_t respectively. The traction along these axes are then given by Eqn. (1), where d is a mixed mode damage parameter that does not allow healing and the condition for t_n prevents overlap of the faces of the element.

$$t_n = \begin{cases} (1-d)K_{penalty}\Delta_n & \text{if } \Delta_n > 0 \\ K_{penalty}\Delta_n & \text{if } \Delta_n \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$t_t = (1-d)K_{penalty}\Delta_t$$

More detailed discussions of Turon's cohesive zone formulation used in this work can be found in Ref. [1] and [7].

2.2 Calculating Fracture Properties for the Next Scale

The goal of these analyses at the fiber/matrix scale is to predict the properties to be used for cohesive zones at the next larger scale, which are the strength and critical strain energy release rate for mode I, II, and III failure. The method used for calculating the fracture properties at the next scale is related to the

method described in Ref. [4] and [5], which proposed the idea that the contribution of elastic deformation should be excluded when calculating the traction separation law for the next scale. Since some details were not given in the references, a few details of the implementation used in this paper are given herein for tensile loads. A volume average strain or applied displacement is applied to the fiber/matrix RVEs. The strength is easy to determine by simply finding the maximum volume average stress out of all of the load steps. From micromechanics, the total volume average strain can be related to the strain in the elastic continuum elements, denoted by ε_{yy}^{cont} , and a surface integral of the separation over the cohesive elements, as given in Eqn. (2). Recall that the total volume average strain is specified and the first term of the right hand side can be easily calculated for the elastic continuum elements. This allows the surface integral term to be calculated from the other two.

$$\langle \varepsilon_{yy} \rangle = \frac{1}{V} \int \varepsilon_{yy}^{cont} dV + \frac{1}{V} \oint u_y^{cz} \cdot n_y dS \quad (2)$$

A separation of the RVE in an average sense can then be given by the surface integral term from Eqn. (2) times the length of the RVE (denoted by L), as given in Eqn. (3), which is the applied displacement minus the contribution to deformation in the respective direction from the continuum elements.

$$\Delta u = \frac{L}{V} \oint u_y^{cz} \cdot n_y dS = L \langle \varepsilon_{yy} \rangle - \frac{L}{V} \int \varepsilon_{yy}^{el} dV \quad (3)$$

Finally, the mode I critical strain energy release rate for the next scale is given by the integral of the traction on the boundary over the average separation, which is given in Eqn. (4). The guidelines proposed in Ref. [7] for the number of load steps and appropriate mesh refinement required for accurate solutions will be used.

$$G_{Ic} = \int t(\Delta u) d(\Delta u) \quad (4)$$

Fig. 2 shows the traction vs Δu curves for the fiber/matrix models and the traction separation curve to be used for cohesive zone elements at the larger scale. The fit was based on matching the peak stress and the area under the curve.

Figure 2: Traction-separation curve from microscale analysis and the curve predicted for next scale using a bilinear fit

Later in this paper it will be shown that the technique used herein based on Ref. [7] to calculate the mode I strain energy release rate for the larger scale does not result in convergence as the RVE size is increased. Preliminary work on predicting the mode II strain energy release rate for use at the larger scale showed an even worse behavior. It is hypothesized that for both mode I and mode II predictions, the presence of diffuse damage is polluting the calculations. For mode II loading the diffuse damage is much greater than for mode I. These concerns will be addressed in future work.

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

This section describes the meshes, boundary conditions, and material properties used for the microscale analyses. Both a simple set of boundary conditions and periodic boundary conditions are described.

3.1 Meshes

Since the fiber/matrix microstructure is assumed to not vary in the direction of the fibers, quasi-3D finite element models are used to model a plane perpendicular to the fibers. This work used a refined triangular element mesh with cohesive elements placed between every continuum element. A typical quasi-3D mesh is shown in Fig. Figure 3.

Figure 3: Typical 500 fiber mesh

In most cases in this paper, periodic boundary conditions will be imposed, which requires that cohesive zone elements to be placed at the left and bottom boundaries of the RVE. Multipoint constraints are then imposed on the boundaries. This allows cracks to grow even along the RVE boundaries.

3.2 Boundary Conditions

This study considered two types of boundary conditions: periodic boundary conditions and simple boundary conditions. Simple boundary conditions for tensile and shear loading of the RVE's are often used for simplicity, not because of correctness. Fig. Figure 4 shows one version of the simple boundary conditions. These boundary conditions assume the RVE is actually symmetric about the x and y axes instead of periodic within the x-y plane. These approximate boundary conditions have been used in previous studies [5] because fully periodic boundary conditions can be difficult to implement in a cohesive model of this nature.

Figure 4: Simple boundary conditions

The fiber/matrix RVE's are generated to be geometrically periodic, so it is possible to exactly impose periodic boundary conditions. Periodic boundary conditions are applied to the unit cell by imposing the relationship in Eqn. (5) on the displacements at the unit cell boundary. Repeated indices imply summation, and d_k is a vector of periodicity that starts at some coordinate x_j in one unit cell and ends at the equivalent point in another unit cell. Angle brackets imply the volume-averaged value of a field variable. A more detailed description of periodic boundary conditions can be found in Ref. [8] and [9]. This work explores the effect of the chosen boundary conditions.

$$u_i(x_j + d_j) = u_i(x_j) + \left\langle \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_k} \right\rangle d_k \quad (5)$$

3.3 Material Properties

The material properties throughout this work are presented in Table 1, where the index 1 denotes the fiber direction (out of plane of the RVE). A range is given for the fiber/matrix interfacial cohesive strengths (denoted by asterisks) because this study considers various strengths to identify the effect of assumed microscale properties on the predicted cohesive properties for the next larger scale. Also, the parameter η is a power law coefficient for the mixed-mode cohesive formulation; see Ref. [1] and [7] for more details.

Fiber Properties ²⁴	
E_{11} (GPa)	276
E_{22} (GPa)	26
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.292
ν_{23}	0.722
$G_{12} = G_{13}$ (GPa)	20.7
G_{23} (GPa)	7.55
$\sigma_{22c} = \sigma_{33c}$ (MPa)	5600
$\sigma_{12c} = \sigma_{13c}$ (MPa)	10000
\mathcal{G}_{Ic} (J/m ²)	5000
\mathcal{G}_{IIc} (J/m ²)	10000
η	1.5

Matrix Properties	
E (GPa)	3.45
ν	0.35

Cohesive Properties ¹⁷	Matrix	Interface
$\sigma_{22c} = \sigma_{33c}$ (MPa)*	77	38.5 - 192.5*
$\sigma_{12c} = \sigma_{13c}$ (MPa)*	100	50 - 250*
\mathcal{G}_{Ic} (J/m ²)	177	177
\mathcal{G}_{IIc} (J/m ²)	496	496
η	2.25	2.25

Table 1: Assumed IM7/5250-4 properties

4 RESULTS

Parametric studies were performed to explore the effects of the choice of boundary conditions, RVE size, and assumed cohesive zone properties.

4.1 Effect of Boundary Conditions

Microscale analyses were conducted for tensile and shear loads using multiple 500 fiber RVE's to determine the effect of boundary conditions. Two sets of boundary conditions were considered, simple boundary conditions and periodic boundary conditions.

4.1.1 Simple Boundary Conditions

Under tensile loads, the simple boundary conditions resulted in a dominant crack initiating from the left and right sides of the RVE. This was the case for all realizations with no dominant crack ever initiating from inside the RVE. This behavior is unrealistic and a cause for concern for the simple boundary conditions. Fig. Figure 5 shows the dominant crack initiation locations for two RVE's under tensile loads.

The predicted strain energy release rate was highly dependent on the offset of the dominant cracks. The greater the vertical distance between the initiation sites of the dominant crack from each side, the farther they must grow to coalesce, which increases the energy dissipated. For example, the RVE on the right of Fig. Figure 5. showed a 58% higher strain energy release rate compared to the one on the left.

Figure 5. Example of typical damage growth under tensile loads using simple boundary conditions (arrows indicate locations of crack initiation)

Under shear loads, the dominant crack initiated in regions very near the upper left or lower right corners of the RVE for all the realizations considered, regardless of features in other places that would be expected to create greater stress concentrations. Fig. Figure 6 shows an example of where the dominant crack initiations and how it grows. This behavior is obviously unrealistic to occur for every RVE. Both the tensile and shear load cases illustrate the dangers in using the simple boundary conditions.

a) Just after formation of dominant crack b) After several load steps of growth
Figure 6. Example of typical damage growth under shear loads using simple boundary conditions

4.1.2 Periodic Boundary Conditions

The periodic boundary conditions alleviated the odd behavior observed when using the simple boundary conditions. There was no preferential location for cracks to form. Under tensile and shear loads, the cracks grew periodically through the boundaries as expected, and a few cases were found where the crack grew along the boundary. The predicted strain energy release rate was heavily dependent on the existence of ligaments carrying load after the dominant cracks formed, as shown in Fig. Figure 7. The apparent large increase in fiber diameter in the ligament region is a plotting artifact due to the large rotation of the region in an analysis that assumes infinitesimal rotation.

a) Early in analysis b) Late in analysis
Figure 7. Example damage growth using periodic boundary conditions with a ligament carrying load

Although the details of the initiation and growth of damage significantly differed between the two sets of boundary conditions, the predicted cohesive properties showed much less sensitivity. The predicted strength differed by a negligible amount (less than 1%), while the predicted strain energy release rate differed by about 10%. If the predicted strength is the only goal of an analysis, the simple boundary conditions might suffice, but periodic boundary conditions are far more appropriate for predicting the damage growth correctly.

4.2 Effect of RVE Size

To select an appropriate RVE size for the progressive damage analyses using cohesive zone elements, the effect of RVE size on the predicted cohesive properties must be identified. In this study, RVE sizes of 10, 100, and 500 were considered. To study the RVE size, the properties listed in Table 1 were used with assumed tensile and shear interfacial cohesive strengths of 77 and 100 MPa respectively.

Since random fiber/matrix RVE's are used, numerous realizations must be considered to obtain an accurate prediction of the average cohesive properties. Stein's two-stage sampling method was used to estimate the number of realizations required [10]. First, 20 realizations were used to estimate the standard deviation. With the estimated standard deviation, the number of realizations was selected to predict the cohesive properties within $\pm 5\%$ of the actual mean with 95% confidence. The number of realizations needed for each RVE size considered is tabulated in Table 2. The number of realizations needed shows an unexpected trend: larger RVE sizes require more realizations to obtain accurate predictions. This might be explained by the ability of larger RVE's to have more variety in the possible damage evolution patterns and thereby more variation of the strain energy release rates. However, this trend poses a problem since each realization is more expensive to analyze for larger RVE's and more RVE's are needed, making the large RVE's prohibitively expensive to analyze.

RVE Size	# Realizations Needed
10 Fibers	21
100 Fibers	15
500 Fibers	31
1000 Fibers	36

Table 2: Number of realizations needed to predict mean within +/- 5% with 95% confidence

Figure 8: Predicted mode I strength and G_c vs. RVE Size

Fig. Figure 8 shows the mean and standard deviation (denoted by the error bars) of the predicted mode I strength and critical strain energy release rate for the different RVE sizes. The predicted RVE strength was insensitive to the RVE size used. This is interesting because previous analyses using different damage

models predicted a strong dependence of strength on RVE size [11]. As the RVE size increased, the predicted G_c continued to increase, which is probably due to more diffuse damage in the larger RVE sizes. However, this poses a significant problem for predicting G_c , since it is unclear what RVE size is appropriate. An open question remains regarding how much of the diffuse damage should be accounted for in G_c , and if so, what RVE size should be used? It has been observed that only one dominant crack forms through a periodic RVE for the analyses considered. Square RVE larger than 500 fibers approach or exceed the thickness of a single ply. Though it is computationally expensive, a section of the ply (periodic only in one direction) could be discretely modelled, which may provide a more physical basis for the selection of RVE size.

4.3 Effect of Microscale Cohesive Properties

The ratio of fiber/matrix interfacial strength to matrix/matrix strength was varied to explore its effect on the predicted RVE strength and strain energy release rate. For this study, the value of the fiber/matrix strength is varied, while the matrix/matrix strength is held constant. Since there is no clear appropriate RVE size, 500 fiber RVEs were used for the results in this section. Only mode I fracture was considered in this section.

Fig. Figure 9 shows resulting cohesive properties for the next scale for various ratios of microscale cohesive properties. The fiber-matrix interface is weaker than the matrix when the ratio is less than 1, making damage along the fiber-matrix interfaces preferable. When the interface is weaker, the predicted G_c was insensitive to the strength since the energy dissipated was relatively the same (the same area of interfaces opened up). However, the predicted strength was very dependent on the interfacial strength.

Figure 9. Predicted mode I strength and G_c vs. ratio of fiber-matrix to matrix-matrix CZ strength using an RVE Size of 500 fibers

There is a region of ratios starting near 1, where significant damage occurs both in the matrix and along the fiber-matrix interface before the formation of a dominant crack, resulting in significant diffuse damage. The amount of diffuse damage is difficult to quantify, but methods are currently being explored to separate the dissipated energy near the dominant crack from that away from the dominant crack, i.e. due to the

diffuse damage. Developing an objective criterion for deciding what damage should be classified as diffuse is likely to be quite important and challenging. The sensitivity of the predicted properties to fiber-matrix strengths continued to decrease as the ratio increased. At some point, the fiber-matrix interface will be strong enough to cause all the damage to occur within the matrix, but a ratio of 2.5 was still not high enough, indicating that stress concentrations and microstructural features forced the crack to grow along the interface. To prevent any damage from occurring on the fiber-matrix interface, a very strong interface would be needed.

These results give an interesting design guideline. When the interface is weaker than the matrix, significant overall strength improvement can be achieved by strengthening the interface, but changing the interfacial strength has little effect on G_{Ic} . When the interface becomes equal or stronger than the matrix, the overall strength is less sensitive to further strengthening of the interface, but significant improvement to G_{Ic} can be achieved by simply improving the strength of the interface.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Using cohesive elements along every element boundary in a fiber/matrix RVE presents many challenges. It was shown that periodic boundary conditions are important for realistic predictions of progressive damage growth and the critical strain energy release rate to be used at the next larger scale. However, the predicted strength of the RVE was insensitive to the boundary conditions used, making simple boundary conditions a viable option if the strength is the only goal of an analysis.

In the study of the effect of RVE size, the number of realizations needed to accurately predict the mean fracture properties for various RVE sizes was determined using Stein's two-stage sampling method. Larger RVE sizes resulted in a larger standard deviation, resulting in the need for more realizations. This becomes quickly prohibitive since large RVEs are expensive and one would need many realizations. The strength was insensitive to the RVE size used, allowing inexpensive analyses to be used to obtain a strength value. However, the critical energy release rate was very sensitive to the RVE size, with larger RVE's resulting in higher values of G_c . It is unclear at this point what RVE size is best to use to predict cohesive properties for the next larger scale.

The fiber-matrix interfacial strength was varied to gain insight into the effect of the constituent fracture properties. It was shown that if the interfacial strength is lower than the matrix strength, overall improvement to the RVE strength can be obtained by strengthening the interface, but the interfacial strength had little effect on the overall G_c . When the interfacial strength is close to or stronger than the matrix strength, an increase in the interfacial strength resulted in an increase of both the overall strength and G_c . These results indicate a complex relationship between a composite's fracture properties and the microscale constituent fracture properties.

Understanding the relationship between properties at the microscale and the fracture properties at the mesoscale still requires significant research. The appropriate RVE size is still unclear. The method for calculation of the fracture properties of an RVE is currently being evaluated more carefully, and a new method to incrementally calculate the dissipated energy for each quadrature point is being developed, which may provide much better accuracy. In addition, there are many other microscale cohesive properties to examine in future parametric studies. The results in this paper are only an early step towards reliable use of cohesive zones in fiber/matrix models for prediction of mesoscale fracture properties.

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